

FORMATION OF COGNITIVE, PEDAGOGICAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS FROM A PSYCHOLOGICAL POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract: This article aims to determine the study and formation of students' cognitive, pedagogical and communicative competences in scientific sources.

Introduction:

Competence (derived from the Latin word "competo" and means "I achieve, I am suitable, I am compatible") is a set of specific knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired by a person. The term competence came into widespread use relatively recently, in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Competence is a requirement for the educational training of a specialist, which is important for carrying out targeted activities in a certain field. It is a state-owned, predetermined social requirement, which is applied to the student's educational preparation, which is important for effective activity in a certain direction. Education focused on the formation of competencies is the ability to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students in a practical way in their personal, professional and social activities. Education based on a competency-based approach enables students to have independence, creativity, active citizenship, initiative, the ability to use media resources and information and communication technologies wisely in their activities, to consciously choose a profession, healthy competition, and general culture. In addition, in the process of mastering each academic subject in education, personal competencies related to the field are also developed in students based on the uniqueness of this subject and the essence of its content. Competence approach, development of all-round competence in personal activity is the main condition of today's social society and education. This requirement is directly related to the professional activity of student-pedagogues. Currently, the main direction of updating the education of the whole world is to be able to see the world, life, and professional activity in a systematic way through an active approach in the educational process, and to perform a certain systematic activity, to solve new problems and tasks. is to develop experience.

Cognitive competence characterizes students' willingness to constantly improve their professional level, ability to independently acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities, apply ideas of independent formation and

regularly enrich their methodological competence. Pedagogical scientist E.S. Zair-Bek defines the process of independent development as "...finding a suitable basis for choosing the right option of a pedagogical decision and directly deriving from the reflection action; it is a sufficient basis for the development of the needs, goals and motives of the subject of pedagogical action, affects the development of his personal qualities and at the same time justifies his attempts to express himself.

The information competence of a teacher, in addition to professional-pedagogical and special knowledge and ways of thinking, provides for the acquisition, processing and application of special skills by a future professional teacher in the process of professional activity. The acquisition of new information technologies, aimed at achieving the diagnosis of the quality of education by using a combination of pedagogical skills, information, methodological, psychophysiological tools and methods, has a special place. The instrumental system of new information technologies is basically a personal computer. It is built on the basis of using the principle of multimedia and hypermedia.

The importance of the acquisition of information competence is that the pedagogue can take into account the advantages of the student, provide a systematic view of the educational activity of each student using multi-level tutorials, automated control systems.

Communicative competence describes the characteristics of communicative activity of a pedagogue, the uniqueness of interaction with future vocational education pedagogues.

Emphasis is placed on the effectiveness of pedagogical activity aimed at achieving didactic goals and communication.

Communicative competence includes methods that help to achieve a high level of communication. They need to be able to understand the role of others in communication activities, show interest in their personality, develop the personality of the future professional education pedagogue, be able to explain their internal situation in terms of behavioral aspects and use non-verbal means of communication (mimicry, pantomime, gestures) signs) to acquire, to be able to take the point of view of the future professional education pedagogue and to be oriented to an environment of trust with another person, to acquire rhetorical methods, to use evaluative, especially disciplinary organized influences, the superiority of the democratic style in the teaching process, being able to look at some aspects of the pedagogical situation with humor.

Social competence is an indicator of the social importance of increasing the level of methodical training, the ability to take responsibility for the proposed new methodical approaches and their application, specific future professional education of personal interests, educational institution, society. It is understood as the manifestation of the relationship with the needs. It describes moral culture, ideals, spiritual values and values. High-level ethical needs and evidence of professional and general self-development are the forces driving the formation of the component of social readiness for independent design of methodological training in future professional education pedagogues; finding one's original task, understood within the framework of an active life position, and caring about it is the feeling of the "right way", precisely the experience that is observed with confidence in the need for self-realization. Management by any administrative methods is not capable of equaling in quality effectiveness with the activity of an independently organized pedagogue based on the social significance of his work, which encourages the achievement of self-set goals through independent design of methodical training, independent selection of methods of achievement. .

After a detailed analysis of the views of scientists on "competence", "professional competence", "project activity", after determining the main components of professional competence (according to A.K. Markova) and the characteristics and structure of project activity, in our work, another, in our opinion, professional We tried to define and explain an important component of competence - project competence.

Project competence, first of all, plays an important role in solving the issues of professional education and ensuring the competitiveness of a modern pedagogue, because it is the knowledge necessary for the preparation and introduction of pedagogical projects that increase the quality of students' education into the educational process, means that it is a sum of abilities and personality traits.

Secondly, the project competence of a pedagogue means a set of competencies that are variable, dynamic, and can be adjusted in time according to changes in the conditions for solving pedagogical tasks that ensure the effectiveness of project activity.

In general, it is expressed in the ability and readiness to apply the experience of project activities in professional practice as a result and is used as part of the general professional and pedagogical competence, the formation of

which is part of all the main directions of the training of future specialists. is used in practice.

Thirdly, project competence is the formation of non-standard project thinking, a high level of acquisition of innovative pedagogical strategies and a high level of acquisition of a complex of project abilities and competencies aimed at adapting to changes in the content, means and methods, and conditions of pedagogical activity.

Conclusion:

The main criterion of cognitive activity is personal motivation, as a result of which the goal of knowledge is formed, the achievement of which is the basis of cognitive independence. It can be concluded that cognitive activity is two interrelated personal qualities characterized by the desire and ability to acquire knowledge and activities without external help. It should be noted that currently the concept of cognitive competence is interpreted differently in pedagogical sciences. Thus, M. I. Mahmutov concludes that cognitive competence is the intellectual ability of a person and the ability to learn and acquire knowledge independently. In addition, the information competence, communicative competence, and social competence of the pedagogue are of great importance for the perfect organization of students' professional activities.

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